

Teaching English Literacy in the Time of COVID-19 Pandemic in Higher Education: A Case Study in Saudi Qassim University

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: October 12, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: December 19, 2020</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords English Literacy, Time of COVID-19, Higher Education, Online Learning</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4374526</p>	<p><i>In the middle of March 2020, thousands of Saudi students have been forced out of universities due to emerging COVID-19 Pandemic and its rapid spread among humans. In these circumstances, the role of e-learning in teaching and learning was clear, as undoubtedly the e-learning with its various applications saved the educational process from non-continuity in many universities, due to using of various E-learning applications like the blackboard application in teaching different academic courses, including literacy (reading and writing) courses for English language majors. This study was conducted to identify how teaching English literacy was and how students were assessed at the time of COVID-19. This study adopts the descriptive research methodology which is appropriately suitable for describing the research topic. The results of the current study indicated that teaching English literacy was not interrupted during the period of study interruption due to the spread of the COVID-19 and this was due to the effective positive impact of e-learning applications, especially the blackboard application not only in teaching but also in providing appropriate various assessment tools for assessing students in English literacy. On the other hand, there were some negatives, including those related to instructors, students, and the e-learning system itself.</i></p>

1. Introduction

The global crisis of COVID-19 has a bad effect in all fields in general and the field of education in particular. Because of the implications of this verse in terms of the widespread spread among people, most countries have taken the necessary precautions to limit this spread. It was clear that the field of education did not stop taking such precautions to preserve the lives of teachers, students, and employees alike. For this reason, the Ministry of Education and Higher Education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia has decided to suspend face-to-face lectures and laboratories in various colleges and universities, and even schools, for fear of spreading the virus infection among students. However, at the same time, the educational process did not stop, but the Ministry of Higher Education made every effort to continue it until the end of the school year in an efficient manner.

E-learning and online pedagogies have become the most appropriate and best solutions for the continuity of the educational process under these emergency circumstances, but most Saudi universities, including the Qasim University, have faced some challenges and difficulties in teaching through e-learning. These difficulties are related to the professor or the student or the new e-learning environment.

1.2. Statement of the Problem

The present study aimed to identify the reality of teaching English literacy in the time of COVID-19 in the department of English language & translation, college of Science & Arts, Qassim University, KSA.

Thus, the present study aimed to answer the following research questions:

R.Q.1. How can English language literacy teaching be continued in Qassim University during the global health crisis (COVID-19)?

R.Q.2. How can EFL Majors' achievement in English language literacy be assessed?

1.3. Literature Review

1.3.1. E-learning in Teaching English Literacy

E-learning is an educational system that enables learners to obtain academic achievement and benefit from the educational process in all its aspects without moving to the study site. It enables the lecturers to deliver information to the learners and discuss with them and appropriate training. It is one of the modes of education characterized by a natural geographical separation between the teacher and the learner. Based on the analysis of online discussions, students appeared to benefit from opportunities for social interaction with peers to improve their CTS and English abilities. **E-learning means that the educational model used is based on the use of electronic media and devices as tools for improving the availability of training, communication, and interaction, and that helps to accept new ways of understanding and learning (Salloum et al., 2019).**

The distance learning system (E-learning) allows the possibility of receiving lectures and lessons from a source far from the venue of the lecture at the same speed and time of implementation, and this system can broadcast the lectures and lessons recorded with high efficiency, so distance learning is a flexible method because it ended the alternatives for learners in terms of the place and time of their learning, it broadens the limits of learning from any place where the learner is.

Through this type of learning, learners can move between the departments that provide information and provide specific activities in the teaching process, and e-learning is one of the methods of distance learning, as it is a creative way to provide an interactive environment centred around learners and well designed in advance, and accessible to the individual in any place and time using the Internet.

English language teaching strategies cannot be separated from the rapid development taking place in information and communication technology, especially e-learning, so, there are many studies that talk about linking e-learning of English language skills, for example, (Villesseche, J., 2019) study. It has demonstrated the effectiveness of using adaptive e-learning tools in developing reading skills (reading comprehension) in writing texts. In addition, Wenyuan's (2017) study has shown that there was a positive impact on learning English vocabulary using mobile applications.

1.3.2. Mobile Learning in Teaching English Literacy

Because of the urgent circumstances specific to the problem of the COVID virus, Qassim University has spared no effort to continue the educational process while preserving the lives of students and professors alike. Given the students, they have had the greatest share of interest and taking into account their financial and social conditions so that they can complete their courses easily.

The university provides its educational applications on different mobile devices (smartphones, tablets, I pads, laptop computers, etc) and different operating systems (Android or I Phone OS). The university has provided such educational applications through various smart devices not only to facilitate students in terms of ease of use, but also because officials are well aware through many published researches of the effectiveness of using these mobile devices in teaching and learning various courses.

Since the primary goal of English language teachers is to link the relationship between the needs of learners and their daily lives, we owe credit to the various mobile devices and the appropriate and easy to use educational applications that carry the desired goal of learning English language (Kukulka-Hulme, Morris & Donohue, 2015). Moreover, There are many studies ((Burston, 2013; Amiryousefi, 2017) and Li, Chu, Ki and Woo, (2010) that have demonstrated the effectiveness of the effect of cooperative learning using computers on the acquisition of writing skills in the English language.

1.4. Research design

In this current study, the researcher used the descriptive research approach, where he described the state of English literacy teaching during the COVID-19 crisis, as well as evaluated students in these skills. Different evaluation skills were described as supported by figures from the blackboard application. The researcher's aim from this description was to obtain the next results.

1.5. Results and Discussion

To answer the first research question, How can English language literacy teaching be continued in Qassim University during the global health crisis (COVID-19)? The researcher presented three effective basic factors to answer this question:

1.5.1. Availability of virtual classes through different e-learning platforms

Qassim University succeeded in facing the challenge of a complete shift towards e-learning during the COVID-19 crisis. It has employed technological applications and specialized educational platforms to broadcast live lectures so that students can complete their lectures, which they interacted with during their explanation by their teacher, in addition to making courses available in the form of videos, presentations, and creating groups on the Facebook site. And WhatsApp to create effective communication channels between students and the professor. The virtual classroom experience has succeeded and has proven to be a fruitful experience and we can activate it, especially in times of crisis, and students who are geographically dispersed. It contributes to enriching the educational process.

Qassim University relied on two basic e-learning applications that provide virtual classes. The two applications are the blackboard (the basic application) and zoom application (the backup application in case of many instructors and students use the blackboard and thus it will be difficult to continue with it so others resort to zoom application.

1.5.1.1. Blackboard System (MLS)

The Blackboard system is one of the most important management learning system (MLS) that Qassim University provided its students and instructors alike. This learning system is very useful and effective as it is available at anytime and anyplace (Rabea Fayeze Faheim Ali, 2017). Moreover, Qassim University decided to create a special website to support the educational platform and develop the site's content, and to add instructions, videos, and training packages directed to the faculty and students around the clock.

The figure consists of two screenshots of the Blackboard LMS interface. The top screenshot shows the 'Home Page' for course ENG 471_1688. It features a navigation menu on the left with items like 'السنة الرئيسية', 'معلومات', 'المقررات', 'التقارير', 'الامتحانات', 'المسرحية', 'الأدوات', 'تلميحات', 'Session 9/3/2020', 'Session 12/3/2020', 'Zoom 16/3/2020', 'Session 19/3/2020', and 'Office Hour Thursday 18/3/2020 10:00AM'. The main content area includes 'Add Course Module', 'My Announcements' (with a notification for ENG 471_1688), 'My Tasks' (showing 'No tasks due'), and 'To Do' (with sections for 'What's Past Due', 'What's Due', and 'Today'). The bottom screenshot shows the 'Needs Attention' section with a notification 'Test Needs Grading' and an 'Alerts' section with 'Past Due' and 'Retention Center Alerts'.

Figure (1) shows the main page from the blackboard system via Qassim university site

Furthermore, the included activities in the curriculum map have been applied in the virtual classes through the use of the university's "Blackboard" platform, which students enjoy using, especially because the platform provides a set of tools such as an interactive presentation of lectures, organizing and controlling the timing of their presentation to students, designing tests and electronically correcting them. , Post important announcements, and respond to students 'messages. Additionally, "Blackboard" is an integrated e-learning management system, as it manages the educational process synchronously and asynchronously, and provides a safe learning environment, teachers provide their decisions and lectures through the addition of multimedia (text, pictures, audio, video, graphics), in which they meet Learners browse content as needed, and communicate with each other through multiple communication tools (Jamilah A. Alokluk,2018).

1.5.1.2. Zoom

Zoom is another e-learning tool that Qassim University provided its students and staff to continue the learning process without stopping at the time of the COVID-19 crisis. It is free, used to organize meetings and meetings where the teacher, lecturer, and businessman help to organize meetings in high quality with the ability to share files with the attendees at the meeting, whether through the teacher, or the learner provided that each individual has his own account.

Figure (2) shows Zoom Main Page via Qassim university site

According to, Al-Kinani, Silwan (2020) there are some advantages to using Zoom in the learning process.

They are:

- 1-To communicate audio and video over the Internet.
- 2-Distance education by displaying the material to be taught via any program, whether it is an educational presentation via pp, word, video, or other training programs, or a screen such as a blackboard that is explained and written on, or a printed book in pdf, with the ability to specify any sentence or text.
- 3-The ability to enter the session via an internet link, with the ability to mute the participants during the speech, or allow some of them to speak.
- 4-The ability to record a video of what is being circulated through the session, and then display it via any social media means of attending it later.

To deal with the Zoom program, the explanation process is done by clicking the Copy URL and sending the link from the teacher to the students, through any means of communication: (WhatsApp, Messenger...). The participants open the link and enter to follow the teacher's explanation. Where the teacher clicks on the shared screen and shares the screen, the video, or any topic he wants to explain, and a whiteboard can use it to write. It records the session by pressing Record.

1.5.2. University English Language Instructors Preparation in Teaching via Virtual Classes

With the spread of COVID-19, Qassim university staff were well prepared to move online. Resources and support to help with this transition are available through university libraries and on Blackboard. It was an electronic faculty training plan to use the Blackboard learning environment. The Deanship of E-Learning, in cooperation with its various units deployed in all faculties of the university, held 323 training courses for the "Blackboard" system and virtual classes in addition to training 4962 university staff from 3/3/2020 to 9/4/2020 to support them during the application period Electronic transformation plan. English language instructors were among the instructors who attended these training courses for e-learning and were keen to discuss the trainers in everything related to how to teach the English language department courses in general and then reading and writing courses in particular.

In teaching English literary (Reading and Writing), Blackboard collaborative System provided direct communication with students via video and audio in a synchronized way across the web, and lectures can be recorded for reference at a later time. After attending some of the training courses for the virtual classes

available through the Blackboard platform on the Qassim University website, teaching professors have become a lot of masters in using the different virtual classroom tools that helped them to teach reading and writing courses effectively and successfully, especially after training students of the English Language and Translation Department The College of Science and Arts in Arras also has an understanding of how to use the virtual classes to learn their courses easily and easily at anytime and anywhere through the mobile devices or desktop computers available with them. Not only the provision of academic content, but also the duties on the blackboard is included and contain the tasks required to be implemented and the method of delivering them electronically and then monitor their grades electronically, which contributes to reducing paper use and reducing the means of virus transmission.

1.5.3. University English language Learners preparation in learning via virtual classes

Qassim University announced its readiness to implement the education system (via distance) directly from undergraduate and postgraduate students in all scientific disciplines, in preparation for confronting emergencies and crises the world is witnessing during this period. This is to ensure the progress of the educational process in all its forms after the suspension of the temporary study of all universities in the Kingdom, through the preparation and implementation of a preparedness plan within the framework of precautionary measures from the new Corona Virus (Covid-19), where the educational process included the creation of virtual classes for all university decisions of various degrees, To fulfil the requirements of the traditional lectures approved in the schedules while ensuring that they are synchronized with their basic times.

Moreover, the use of technology and electronic educational platforms as a whole is not new to students, "since the beginning of the year, and before we faced the crisis (of Corona), students had to choose less than two courses for distance teaching." Qassim University provided workshops and training courses on virtual classes to prepare for entry at any moment in the virtual classes, as well as the establishment of experimental tests to ensure students' knowledge of the technology. It noted the decision of the Saudi Ministry of Education, which had the primary role when it decided to facilitate students by reducing the degree of quarterly exams, and replacing them with continuous evaluation of duties, projects, and short tests. She pointed out that universities have created options for other programs that universities have made free contributions to continue the education process.

To answer the second research question, how can EFL Majors' achievement in English language literacy be assessed?

When the decision of the final exam was issued remotely because of COVID-2019, the students did not invade fear. On the contrary, the tests across the virtual classes proved successful, even if the grades were not essential in them. It was agreed to ensure credibility, such as the specified period, not to refer to the previous question, and to put random questions.

The decision of the Ministry of Education in Saudi Arabia to remotely evaluate the final exams mechanism in the period of suspension of the study was due to "COVID-19", as it achieved high flexibility for students, especially at the level of achievement of degrees, as the latest tests will be formed for all universities and vocational training centres, scheduled for April 26 Present, the equivalent of 20 percent of total annual collections.

Concerning answering the second research question related to how English Language Department students can be evaluated in literacy (reading and writing) skills, the Department of English and Translation at the Qassim University recommends increasing the marks assigned to the semester work for the course to be 80 marks of the total college marks and 20 marks for the final exam.

According to the university's vision in terms of teaching and evaluating all courses through the e-learning platforms available on the official website, it was necessary for instructors who teach English reading and writing courses to follow the same methods of evaluation of the rest of the department's courses, which is evaluated through the Blackboard e-learning platform, which contains a section for student assessment. (see figure 3).

Figure (3) shows an assessment section in Blackboard Application

This section includes all available assessment tools that instructors can use them to evaluate their students in reading and writing courses. These tools include essay questions, multiple-choice questions, true or false questions, either or, file a response, fill in multiple blanks, fill in the blanks, rumbled sentences, matching, multiple answers, ordering, and short answer. From the researcher's point of view, the available assessment tools on the blackboard include some that suit reading course (like multiple choice questions, true or false questions, fill in multiple blanks, fill in the blanks, rumbled sentences, matching, multiple answers) and writing (like essay questions, multiple choice questions, and short answers questions) courses.

Figure (4) shows different kinds of creation questions

Once the instructor checks the tests, the Blackboard system sends notifications of the student's grades and the student has the right to object to his mark by contacting the teacher via a message through the Blackboard system or sending a message via the official university email.

28.5 / 40**Current Grade**

Based on submitted work

إجمالي

Tap for more detail

28.5 / 40Marks of the first in-
class writing

31/03/2020, 5:41 PM

3.5 / 5**The first Quiz**

24/03/2020, 9:58 PM

7 / 10**essay**

31/03/2020, 5:41 PM

0 / 5**Mid-Term Exam**

31/03/2020, 9:42 AM

18 / 20

Figure (5) notifications of the student's grades

1.6. Obstacles of Using the Blackboard System in Teaching and Assessment English Literacy

There is no doubt that any new educational system has some difficulties in its application, especially if it is an electronic educational system such as the Blackboard system. These obstacles were related to university instructors as some of them dealt with an unfamiliar technique and others suffered from the lack of necessary training and experience in the field of information and communication technology because the time of moving to teach via e-learning was not enough to be perfect in all blackboard tools in teaching or assessing their students.

Moreover, Lack of specialists in e-learning, and poor technical support, Lack of incentive, incentives, lack of experience in using it, students' lack of response to e-learning, ease of penetration of content and tests, students' lack of computers and the Internet, poor qualification of technicians, weak and interrupted internet. Among the constraints that faculty members have faced is the sheer volume of pressures and burdens incurred by faculty members, and the efforts made by the professor to ensure that the required information reaches students in all possible ways and means, and to make sure that any difficulty affecting the student's understanding of the scientific subject, in addition to the reports and tasks assigned to him from Before administering the college, which she must deliver daily.

(Al-Ruwaily, Abdulaziz bin Shreth Hussain, 2018)

Also, one of the problems that faced English language instructors in assessing the writing course was the various methods of cheating that some students use, such as direct cheating from the textbook or cheating from the Internet (especially in the essay question) where students copy and paste the essay they are required to write through the writings of others available on the Internet. The teacher of this course tried to stop as much as possible the process of cheating in the essay question as he used the program to detect quotes and the teacher sent the results of this program to students quoted from the writings of others and they were warned to repeat such behavior in the next tests. As a result of the teacher's use of such a tool, these students stopped cheating from the Internet in answering the essay question. As for the rest of the other types of questions, the teacher evaluated the students in the same content of the course, but with the change of vocabulary and the formulation of the questions in the same course.

Figure (6) shows an instructor's notes to a plagiarizer student

On the other side, the teachers who teach reading course, they tried to prevent students from cheating by narrowing the time of the tests and not displaying all the test questions in one screen and displaying them in a different order among students and pressing the option not to return to the question after completing it Also, he offered one attempt to answer the question, not multiple attempts. As for the contents of the same questions, the teacher changed the vocabulary of the questions and wrote questions based on understanding, not memorization. All of these are attempts by instructors who teach writing and reading courses to stop the fraud process, and to have transparency and fairness in the evaluation process through e-learning in light of the crisis of COVID 19.

In addition, there were some obstacles related to the blackboard and internet like slow internet speed, difficulty entering lectures and exams due to poor internet connection in some areas where some students live, and Blackboard platform glitch due to massive pressure on the site. Despite all the attempts made by the Ministry of Education and the University Administration that would be in the interest of the student, unfortunately, we face many problems of neglect by some students who fail to enter lectures and tests, and it is difficult to reach them and communicate with them to try to compensate for the results of this neglect, which it makes the evaluation process difficult.

Based on the foregoing, it can be said: Despite the difficulties and obstacles that students and faculty members faced in the decision to switch to distance learning, it was the optimal decision that ensures the continuity of the educational process in such a crisis, and that the government of Saudi Arabia was able to manage the crisis effectively, and to confront it positively and productively, ensuring the future of its students and achieving their interests.

Conclusion

The current study tried to describe how to continue to teach English literacy among English majors, students during the COVID-19 crisis as soon as how to assess students' achievements in English literary at Qassim University. The results of the current study answered the two research questions.

For the first research question, the results of the research proved that Qassim University represented by the Department of English and Translation at the College of Sciences and Arts in Arras was able to continue English literacy teaching to EFL majors by providing electronic learning systems (Blackboard - Zoom) where the contents of the curricula were uploaded through the content sections in these systems, in addition to that, there are teaching aids that instructors can use to help his students to understand the courses' requirements. The researcher described the great effort made by Qassim University to continue the educational process through the use of e-learning applications during this crisis.

Moreover, he has presented all the capabilities (e-learning applications - technological evaluation tools - training courses for teachers - training courses for learners) made available by Qassim University. On the other side, the researcher also presented challenges (weak internet - lack of sufficient time for training on these systems - weakness in evaluation tools) that some faced while using these different electronic systems at that period. Accordingly, in the related studies section, he presented some studies (Kukulka-Hulme, Morris & Donohue, 2015; Villesseche, J., 2019; Wenyuan, 2017) that supported using e-learning in learning process, especially with English literacy (Li, Chu, Ki and Woo, 2010; Burston, 2013; Amirousefi, 2017) that proved the effectiveness of using e-learning applications in teaching and learning.

For the second research question, via our current descriptive study, we have shown that different assessment tools can be used to check students' achievements in English literacy courses (reading and writing) and that these assessment tools are reliable, valid and authentic. Moreover, the results of the study have shown that the assessment tools that are available within electronic applications (blackboard and Zoom) proved their effectiveness when instructors used them to evaluate their students in English literary courses except for a defect (cheating in online exams) which is not specific for these applications only, but only for the evaluation of students remotely. These results of the current study are in line with (Cabiness, Irvine, & Grove, 2013; Van Heerden & Van der Merwe, 2017; Wiliam, 2011) studies that confirmed the importance of e-learning system in higher education institutions.

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